

State-of-affairs of the Belgian protein transition

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Table of Contents

1	Introduction	7
1.1	<i>What is this report about?</i>	7
1.2	<i>What are proteins?</i>	7
1.3	<i>What is the current consumption of proteins in Belgium?</i>	8
1.4	<i>What is the protein transition?</i>	9
1.5	<i>What are barriers of consumers to the protein transition?</i>	11
2	Which key actors do and could accelerate the protein transition?	13
2.1	<i>Processors</i>	14
2.2	<i>Wholesalers, food service and food retailers</i>	16
3	How do and could actors accelerate the protein transition?	16
3.1	<i>Build an alliance</i>	16
3.2	<i>Build a shared vision for the future</i>	17
3.3	<i>Build intervention strategies on how to reach that future</i>	18
3.3.1	Type of interventions	18
3.3.2	Food product categories to promote in interventions	21
4	Why do Belgian actors want to accelerate the protein transition?	23
5	What issues does the protein transition help to address?	26
5.1	<i>Limiting global warming</i>	26
5.2	<i>Limiting other environmental problems</i>	27
5.3	<i>Improving public health</i>	27
5.4	<i>Guaranteeing food security for the growing world population & improving social justice in the world</i>	29
5.5	<i>Developing the economy: developing the image of organisations, developing economically as organisation, developing the Belgian economy, becoming more strategically independent of other countries</i>	29
5.6	<i>Improving animal welfare and protection</i>	29
6	(Inter)governmental policy initiatives	30
6.1	<i>International</i>	30
6.1.1	Sustainable Development Goals	30
6.1.2	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change reports	31
6.1.3	World Health Organisation research	31
6.2	<i>European Union</i>	31
6.2.1	EU Common Agriculture Policy	31
6.2.2	European Green Deal and Climate Law	32
6.2.3	EU Circular Economy Action Plan	33
6.2.4	EU Regulation On Deforestation-Free Products	33
6.2.5	EU Industrial Emission Directive	34
6.2.6	EU Taxonomy Regulation for sustainable activities	34
6.2.7	EU Novel Food regulation	34
6.2.8	EU Directive on CSRD and CS3D	34
6.2.9	EU Dietary guidelines	34
6.2.10	EU subsidies for research and training	35
6.3	<i>Belgian federal government</i>	35
6.3.1	Federal sustainable development policy	35
6.3.2	Federal climate policy	36
6.3.3	Federal dietary guidelines	37

6.3.4	Federal subsidies for research and training	37
6.4	<i>Flemish government</i>	37
6.4.1	Flemish sustainable development policy	37
6.4.2	Flemish food strategy	38
6.4.3	Flemish Green Deal Protein Shift on our plate	38
6.4.4	Flemish climate policy	38
6.4.5	Flanders circular economy	39
6.4.6	Flemish subsidies for research and training	39
6.5	<i>Walloon government</i>	39
6.5.1	Walloon sustainable development policy	39
6.5.2	Walloon food strategy	39
6.5.3	Walloon Green Deal Sustainable Canteens	40
6.5.4	Walloon climate policy	40
6.5.5	Walloon circular economy	40
6.5.6	Walloon subsidies for research and training	40
6.6	<i>Brussels-Capital Region government</i>	41
6.6.1	Brussels-Capital sustainable development policy	41
6.6.2	Brussels-Capital food strategy	41
6.6.3	Brussels-Capital climate policy	42
6.6.4	Brussels-Capital circular economy	42
6.6.5	Brussels-Capital funding for research and training	42
6.7	<i>Local governments</i>	42
6.7.1	Flemish local governments	42
6.7.2	Walloon local governments	42
6.7.3	Brussels-Capital local governments	43
7	References	45
8	Appendices	54
	<i>Appendix 1: List of abbreviations</i>	54
	<i>Appendix 2: List of actors</i>	54

1 Introduction

1.1 What is this report about?

This report provides information on the context in which the protein transition takes place in Belgium, a European country in the Global North. In this report we define this transition as the change in ratio of consumption between animal and plant-based proteins towards more plant-based, while reducing the total protein consumption. This dietary shift is a pathway to more sustainable and healthy food consumption.

In this report we first introduce the issues (section 1.2-1.5), then we define who could accelerate the protein transition and how (section 2-3), subsequently we define why actors want to contribute (section 4-5). Lastly, in section 5, we present an overview of the policy initiatives with implications for the Belgian protein transition. For this last section, the scope is broadened to from production to consumption to take the systemic approach.

The data for this report was collected through deskwork (see references, and list of abbreviations in Appendix 1), through our own consumer research using an online survey, and through our evaluation research using an online survey and interviews with actors. SFERE (KU Leuven) mostly collected the data for Flanders, Belgium and Europe; SYTRA (UCLouvain) contributed by providing data for Wallonia.

This report is one of the deliverables of the Futures4Food project financed by BELSPO through the research programme BRAIN-be 2.0 (Belgian Research Action through Interdisciplinary Networks). Futures4Food aimed to develop future scenarios and transition pathways for the Belgian cereal and protein transition-related sectors to become more sustainable. It also supported actors in developing skills to address the complexity of the food system. The research partners of the project were KU Leuven (IF, Institute for the Future, and SFERE, Sustainable Food Economies Research Group), UCLouvain (SYTRA) and Flanders Business School. The project ran from January 2020 to June 2025. This report does not intend to be complete, but to provide an overview with the intention to be useful for different actors who want to contribute to the acceleration of the protein transition.

1.2 What are proteins?

Proteins are specific molecules that play essential roles in biological processes, also in our own bodies for several regulatory processes and for the construction of our cells. They are required in large amounts in our diet, therefore they are grouped with the macronutrients, together with fat and carbohydrates. Proteins also provide us with energy (calories): 17 kJ or 4 kcal per gram of protein. Almost all food contains proteins, both animal-based food (such as meat, seafood, milk and eggs) and plant-based food (such as grains, pulses, nuts and seeds) (Hoge Gezondheidsraad, 2016).

On average, the body of an adult person is built up of 12 kilogram of protein. The Population Reference Intake (PRI) is set at consuming 0.83 gram of protein per kg of bodyweight per day for adults of all ages. However, some people require a larger intake of protein per kg of bodyweight: being in certain life stages (such as children or pregnant women), performing certain activities (such as athletes) or having certain conditions or wounds (such as burns). A short-term consequence of a deficit in protein is the breakdown of muscle tissue. On the long term, it leads to a lack of muscle strength and reduced immunity. Additionally, for children a long-term deficiency could cause growth disorders. This most often happens in countries in the Global South (EFSA NDA Panel, 2015; Voedingscentrum, 2024). The safe upper limit for healthy adults is eating 2 gram of protein per kg of bodyweight per day. Eating more could cause issues with digestion, kidneys, and blood vessels (Wu, 2016).

1.3 What is the current consumption of proteins in Belgium?

In Belgium most citizens eat more proteins than needed. The most recent Belgian National Food Consumption Survey (BNFCS) (n=3777, aged 3+, 2022-2023) revealed that on average a Belgian citizen consumes 69 gram of protein per day (Bel et al., 2025a). It appears that 95.6% of women and 98.6% of men exceed the guidelines calculated by the EFSA based on the body weight reference values (Departement Landbouw & Visserij, 2023).

Apart from this overconsumption, Belgians consume more animal-based proteins compared to plant-based proteins (Bel et al., 2025b). According to this BNFCS of 2022-2023, the most important sources of protein were meat and plant-based substitutes (35%), cereals and grain products (21%) and milk products and substitutes (17%) (Bel et al., 2025a). The average consumption per day was 151 grams of milk products, 37 grams of processed meat for a hot meal, 24 grams of poultry, 23 grams of meat charcuterie, 20 grams of unprocessed red meat and 4 grams of meat replacement products like tofu and veg(eteri)an meat analogues (Bel et al., 2025b; sciensano.be, 2025).

We have also studied the current consumption of meat products and plant-rich meat analogues with a clear meat-like structure and taste through an online questionnaire with 18-64 year-old meat-eating citizens of the Flemish Region (2024, n=1050, unpublished), see Table 1 and 2.

Table 1: Consumption frequency [%] of five categories of meat products by 18-64 year-old meat eating citizens from the Flemish Region

	Unprocessed meat with a hot meal, e.g., steak, cutlet, and chicken	Processed meat with a hot meal, e.g., sausage, burger, nugget, and bacon	Processed meat as a snack, e.g., bitter ball and appetiser sausage	Charcuterie sandwich fillings e.g., ham, salami, and luncheon meat	Spreadable meats as sandwich fillings, e.g., chicken curry, prepared mince, pate, and meat salad
Never	1.90	3.05	17.52	5.62	8.29
< 1 day/week	14.86	24.76	67.52	20.38	35.62
1-2 days/week	42.00	51.81	12.10	24.86	33.62
3-4 days/week	31.81	17.05	0.76	25.14	13.90
5-6 days/week	6.95	1.52	0.00	14.38	5.24
Every day	1.81	0.86	0.00	9.14	2.95
No idea	0.67	0.95	2.10	0.48	0.38

Source: unpublished work of Futures4Food, 2024

Table 2: Consumption frequency [%] of five categories of plant-rich meat analogues by 18-64 year-old meat eating citizens from the Flemish Region

	Meat analogues with a hot meal, e.g., veg(etarian) chicken	Meat analogues with a hot meal, e.g., veg(etarian) sausage, burger, nugget, and bacon	Meat analogues as a snack, e.g., veg(etarian) bitter ball and appetiser sausage	Meat analogues as charcuterie sandwich fillings, e.g., veg(etarian) ham, salami, and luncheon meat	Spreadable meat analogues as sandwich fillings, e.g., veg(etarian) chicken curry, prepared mince, pate, and meat salad
Never	72.10	69.90	84.29	84.29	81.43
< 1 day/week	20.67	22.76	13.81	11.26	13.52
1-2 days/week	4.76	5.52	0.57	2.19	2.76
3-4 days/week	1.14	0.86	0.19	0.38	0.57
5-6 days/week	0.19	0.10	0.10	0.19	0.10
Every day	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.10	0.19
No idea	1.14	0.86	1.05	0.95	1.43

Source: unpublished work of Futures4Food, 2024

The results show that the number of meat-eating respondents who regularly consumed meat analogues (at least once a week) is rather low, ranging across different categories from 0.9% to 6.5% (Table 2). Meat analogues mimicking unprocessed and processed meat products in hot meals are consumed most (6.1% and 6.5% respectively, ≥ 1 day/week) (Table 2). For their corresponding meat products, respectively 82.6% and 71.2% reports consuming these at least weekly (Table 1).

The ‘CO-MEET’ research (n=2192 Flemish adults, 2021-2022) shows that the willingness to replace animal-based by plant-based food is higher for women, young and highly educated people. Intriguingly, people show a higher replacement intention if they are accompanied with friends (compared to family) (Coucke & Slabbinck, 2024).

Interestingly, according to the ‘draagvlakmonitor’ (n=1468, 2023), 81% of the Flemish meat-eating population is eating vegetarian main meals 1-3 days per week and 14% 4-6 days per week (Vansteenkiste et al., 2023). In 2024, 6% of the Belgian 18-64 year-olds consume either vegetarian (so not eating animals, but do eating products derived from animals such as milk, cheese and eggs) or vegan (so exclusively eating plant-based food) on daily basis. This number was higher in Brussels (19%, n=100), compared to Wallonia (6%, n=320) and Flanders (3%, n=570) (VLAM, 2024d).

1.4 What is the protein transition?

In this report we define the protein transition as a change of the ratio of consumption between animal and plant-based proteins towards more plant-based, while reducing the total protein consumption in Belgium. The protein transition narrative differs between regions and academic papers. Others may also include transitioning the production and transitioning towards other non-traditional protein sources such as fungi, insects and algae. In high-income countries, three main narratives are found according to Duluins & Baret, 2024, p1 (see Figure 1): “(1) the consumer narrative focusing on consumption-based solutions targeting dietary changes; (2) the techno-centred narrative developing new, more resource-

efficient protein production systems; and (3) the socio-technological narrative that intends to transition the agri-food system from an animal-dominated regime to an alternative protein regime”. The definition used in this report relates to the first and most common narrative, since it is consumer-focused. Yet, it also connects with the third narrative, since it does not only have consumers and civil society as the primary initiators, but all actors of the food system using multi-actor collaboration.

Figure 1: The three narratives of the protein transition in high-income countries
The left side depicts the present state and narratives of the protein transition, featuring examples of action pathways. The right side shows the primary challenges targeted by the protein transition. The lines represent the interactions between narratives and challenges.
Source: Duluins & Baret, 2024

To reach a more sustainable food system, the protein transition is advised in the Global North, since high levels of animal products are consumed in these countries (Ritchie et al., 2023). According to the Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO) of the United Nations (UN) a ‘sustainable food system’ can be defined as follows (Nguyen, 2018, p1):

“Food system that delivers food security and nutrition for all in such a way that the economic, social and environmental bases to generate food security and nutrition for future generations are not compromised. This means that:

It is profitable throughout, it has broad-based benefits for society, and it has a positive or neutral impact on the natural environment.”

1.5 What are barriers of consumers to the protein transition?

One of the reasons that the protein transition is challenging for consumers, is that it asks for a change in habitual behaviour, which is harder than for example installing solar panels once (Vansteenkiste et al., 2023). Besides that, the protein transition is challenging because it asks consumers to balance benefits such as health and sustainability with perceived drawbacks such as worse taste, higher costs, and inconvenience (Grunert, 2011). Most people rank 'pleasure' as the most important factor for choosing their food, followed by 'cost', 'health', 'convenience' and lastly 'conscience' (according to the 'VLAM-tracking' of 2024 of 1000 Belgian citizens of 18-64 year) (VLAM, 2024c). Consequently, this contributes to a gap between consumer's values, attitudes, intentions, and their actual behaviour (Vermeir et al., 2020). While many consumers today care about their health and the environment, their food choices often do not align with these concerns, leading to what is called the 'intention-behaviour gap'. Consumers have some control over their food choices but are also influenced by contextual factors. So, barriers to change exist both on an individual level –low motivation or capabilities– and at a contextual level –lack of physical and social opportunities. These individual and contextual level factors interact closely (Warde, 2005).

Figure 2 outlines common consumer barriers in Europe. While countries show slight differences, the main challenges are similar. However, there are large differences across consumer groups within countries, and not everyone is equally engaged in sustainable and healthy eating (SAPEA, 2023).

Motivation:

- Liking and preferences: strong liking of meat and animal products (taste, texture, ...), disliking of plant-based foods (influence of social and cultural norms)
- Attitudes: positive attitudes towards meat and animal products, negative attitudes towards plant-based foods (influence of social and cultural norms and conventions)
- Perceived benefits & risks: for example, belief that (large amounts of) meat and animal foods are necessary for a healthy diet
- Perceived high prices of meat substitutes and vegetables (compared to animal products)
- Scepticism and prejudice towards the terms/labels 'vegetarian' and 'vegan'
- Lack of environmental or climate concern
- Lack of perceived responsibility or obligation
- Lack of perceived behavioural control
- Emotions and affect: positive emotions linked to meat and animal products, negative emotions linked to plant-based foods
- Negative expectations about outcomes (for example, costly, little self-efficacy, no environmental effect, unhealthy)

Capability:

- Food familiarity:
 - ▶ Lack of familiarity with novel foods
 - ▶ Prior experiences/aversion/liking
 - ▶ Food neophobia
- Lack of skills (planning, acquisition, storing, preparing, cooking e.g. meat-free recipes)
- Lack of nutrition-related knowledge (planning, acquisition, storing, preparing, cooking)
- Physiological factors such as hunger, satiety or appetite linked to meat and animal products
- Lack of knowledge about environmental, climate and health impacts of meat consumption
- Self-regulation (lack of self-control) — personality trait: lack of conscientiousness leads to impulsive eating and loss of self-control
- Difficulty or inability to change habits and routines
- Lack of time (throughout all consumption phases, for example, to try new meat-free recipes)

Opportunity:

■ Physical environment:

- ▶ Perceived low availability and low salience/visibility of plant-based alternatives in supermarkets, canteens, restaurants etc.
- ▶ Perceived inconvenience of plant-based alternatives
- ▶ Prominent positioning and omnipresence of meat and animal products in supermarkets, canteens, restaurants etc.
- ▶ Prices (cheap meat products - possible through subsidies and industrial factory farming?)
- ▶ Visual cues, smells or other sensory stimuli (affect perception of portion size, intake or satiation)
- ▶ Large portion sizes of meat and animal products by default
- ▶ Difficult accessibility of plant-based foods (e.g., unattractive labelling and naming/framing, e.g. as 'vegan' or 'vegetarian')
- ▶ Obesogenic/unsustainable environments (e.g., neighbourhoods with higher density of fast-food outlets and lower density of supermarkets and grocery stores - so-called food-deserts)

■ Social environment:

- ▶ Lack of support for eating plant-based eating foods from close others (family, friends, colleagues)
- ▶ Social norms ("meat = default")
- ▶ Food culture and tradition: Meat is traditionally part of the food culture in European countries
- ▶ Social prejudice
- ▶ Social identity and lifestyles determined by food consumption
- ▶ Symbolic meaning of meat (e.g. red meat symbolises human power)

Sources: Appleton et al., 2016; Bauer & Reisch, 2019; Benelam, 2009; Bucher et al., 2016; Chen & Antonelli, 2020; Evers et al., 2018; Graça et al., 2019; Munt et al., 2017; Nguyen et al., 2022; Stautz et al., 2018; Stoll-Kleemann & Schmidt, 2017.

Figure 2: Barriers to reducing the consumption of meat and animal foods and increasing plant-based foods consumption, in European countries

Source: SAPEA, 2023

2 Which key actors do and could accelerate the protein transition?

Many actors can have a role to play in accelerating the protein transition, minor or major. First, we provide an overview of food supply chain actors of the Belgian plant protein sector. These actors are involved from production to consumption or disposal. The **producers** are at the base of the food supply chain. In plant-based agriculture, farm inputs are used to produce primary food commodities, such as vegetables, fruits, grains, pulses, seeds, nuts and aquatic plants. Plant-based food can either be used for direct human consumption or for further processing. In the processing phase, these commodities are transformed into other food products and packaged by **processors** (section 2.1). Then, the **wholesalers** (section 2.2) buy these food products in large quantities and redistribute it to **food service and food retailers** (section 2.2). Subsequently, they sell food to **consumers**. Food donations happen via food redistributors. To connect the different actors and stages, transportation and storage is mostly required. Shorter food supply chains are also possible via for example farmers' markets and community-supported agriculture (HLPE, 2017).

Beside food supply chain actors, also **knowledge institutes** are influencing the food supply chain by providing knowledge and insights. They comprise of higher education and research institutes. For production and processing of food, knowledge institutes are crucial to gain knowledge on how to obtain an end product that is produced more efficiently, healthy, tasty and sustainably (Technopolis & Blonk Consultants, 2018; Unity Environmental University, 2025). Also customer behaviour is researched to increase the willingness to try and consume plant-rich protein products (Coucke et al., 2022, 2023; Coucke & Slabbinck, 2024).

Likewise, the different **government bodies** (level of Europe, Belgium, Flemish Region, Walloon Region, Brussels-capital Region or cities) influence the food supply chain, through among others policy instruments and funding (SAPEA, 2023). More information on the current policies can be found in section 6.

Also **non-profit organisations** have a role to play in the protein transition. They can for example increase the motivation of food actors to carry out interventions to accelerate the protein transition and engage in policy and environmental advocacy (BeVegan, 2025; ProVeg, 2025; The Next Food Chain, 2019).

Finally, all actors are acquiring food literacy via among others **primary and secondary school, healthcare providers** and **media channels** (HLPE, 2017). A list of actors currently engaging in accelerating the protein transition in Belgium can be found in Appendix 2. Now, we elaborate on two actor categories that are particularly key in the protein transition.

2.1 Processors

In Belgium, there are several processing companies transforming commodities into plant-rich intermediary and finished food products. These products can be processed through e.g., canning, vacuum packaging, refrigerating, cooking or extracting protein (Wullaert et al., 2024).

Plant-based processors such as millers and bakers have a limited role in the protein transition, whereas processors contributing to final products such as plant-rich meat- or fish replacements, plant-based dairy and egg replacements, plant-rich spreads, and nut and seed pastas are playing a substantial role as they can change food composition and increase the physical availability of tasty products (Wullaert et al., 2024). Not only plant-based processors contribute to the protein transition, but also meat and dairy processing companies in Belgium started to offer vegetarian or vegan products (Aoste.be, 2025; tijd.be, 2016).

Further exploration:

Wullaert et al., 2024 provides an overview of plant-rich processing companies in Flanders and Brussels and its economic impact.

Some processors provide plant-rich meat replacement products ('MRPS'), food products that largely consist of plant-based proteins and that have the purpose of replacing meat. There are different types of meat replacement products (Good Food Institute, 2021; Jang & Lee, 2024; Technopolis & Blonk Consultants, 2018):

- **Pulses, nuts and seeds:**
Direct consumption or after cooking, e.g., chickpeas.
- **1st generation meat replacement products:**
 - Tofu: processed product from soy, similar to the processing of cheese.
 - Tempeh: processed product from fermented soy.
 - Seitan: processed product from gluten.
- **2nd generation meat replacement products:**
Processed products in the shape of meat, but without the taste or texture of meat, e.g., ready-made vegetarian or vegan burgers, sausages or balls.
- **3rd generation meat replacement products ('plant-based meat analogues'):**
Processed products with a clear meat-like structure and taste. To mimic the fibrous texture of meat, protein reforming techniques such as extrusion, shear cells and 3D printing are used. Extrusion and shear cell technologies rely on varying temperatures and pressures, while 3D printing builds products layer by layer. To further enhance the taste, appeal and texture, extra ingredients are added: flavouring agents, fats, binding agents, texturisers and colouring agents.

- **Hybrid products:**
Processed products with both animal-based and plant-based proteins.

In recent years, also plant-based fish analogues are produced. These are processed products with a clear fish-like structure and taste. Production methods similar to those for plant-based meat analogues are used (Mahmud et al., 2024). Table 3 shows the main plant protein ingredients for these products and the MRPS.

Table 3: Overview of main plant protein ingredients used for plant-rich meat replacement products and fish analogues, for example to obtain the meat- or fish-like structure or to increase the protein content of the end product

Protein source group	Protein source	Usage
Pulses For MRPS: used to make flour, protein concentrate and protein isolate	Soy	For direct consumption, for 1 st , 2 nd and 3 rd generation MRPS, hybrid products and plant-based fish analogues
	Peas	For direct consumption, for 2 nd and 3 rd generation MRPS, hybrid products and plant-based fish analogues
	Field and white beans	For direct consumption, for 2 nd and 3 rd generation MRPS, hybrid products and plant-based fish analogues
	Chickpeas	For direct consumption, mostly used for falafel (sometimes 2 nd and 3 rd generation MRPS and hybrid products) and plant-based fish analogues
By-products of the starch industry	Wheat protein	for 1 st , 2 nd and 3 rd generation MRPS, hybrid products and plant-based fish analogues
	Potato protein	mostly used as texturiser, as a replacer for chicken egg white
Seeds	Hemp seed	Direct consumption, sometimes for 2 nd generation MRPS and hybrid products and plant-based fish analogues
	Quinoa	Direct consumption, sometimes for 2 nd generation MRPS
Aquatic plants	Seaweed	Direct consumption, as protein ingredient in composite products and plant-based fish analogues

Sources: Boukid et al., 2024; Good Food Institute, 2021; Mahmud et al., 2024; Technopolis & Blonk Consultants, 2018

For making plant-based milk, usually a plant protein source is mixed, heated and homogenised together with flavouring agents, oil, binding agents, texturisers, vitamins, minerals and water. Common protein sources for plant-based milk are oat, rice, soy, coconut, lupin, chickpea and field beans. For producing plant-based yoghurt a fermentation step is a necessary additional step, whereas for plant-based cheese a ripening step is required. Plant-based cheese consists of more starch (e.g., from potato) and fat (e.g., from coconut or cashew), compared to plant-based milk or yoghurt. For producing plant-based egg replacements, different processing steps are required depending on the application, for example pasteurising mung beans (Good Food Institute, 2021).

Making plant-rich spreads and nut and seed pastas mostly involves a combination of blending, emulsification and heat treatment (Ghosal et al., 2022; Winkler-Moser et al., 2022).

2.2 Wholesalers, food service and food retailers

Wholesalers buy in bulk and redistribute to food service and food retailers. They also have a role in the protein transition, as they can influence the selling behaviour of their providers and the purchasing behaviour of their clients through negotiating pricing and availability (SAPEA, 2023). Food service companies and food retailers have an important role to play in the protein transition too, as they can influence both demand and supply to consumers. Food service companies include hotels, restaurants (including quick service), cafés, street food vending, caterers (also in hospitals and schools) and online prepared food delivery. Food retailers are supermarkets, specialty stores, convenience stores and online food shops (including foodbox companies) (SAPEA, 2023).

The 'Consumptietracker' of VLAM (n=7300 Belgian 18-65-year-old citizens, 2024) reports that 72% of the hot meals were prepared at home, while 8% were bought ready-made for heating up at home, 8% were take-away or delivered, and 12% was out-of-home consumption. This study also shows the increased share and importance of food service. Especially in Brussels, as the take-away-delivery and out-of-home proportion is even higher there: 11% and 15% respectively (n=600) (VLAM, 2024a).

The 'CPS GFK' study (n=3000 households, 2023) reports that 78% of purchases of fresh food for home consumption took place in supermarkets by Flemish citizens, showing the importance of supermarkets. Only 16% of these purchases happened in specialised channels (like bakers, butchers and vegetable stores), the rest happened among others via markets and short supply chains. The same study also shows another trend to keep an eye on for the protein transition: 37% of the households has purchased a meal box before (via the supermarket or online, including a recipe and ingredients), an increase of one third since 2016 (Michiels, 2024).

Interestingly, the quickest and most cost effective way for the food retail sector to comply with the Directive on Corporate Sustainability Reporting (see 5.1.2.8) is rebalancing protein offerings to support plant-rich diets (Madre Brava, 2025).

3 How do and could actors accelerate the protein transition?

We propose to build an alliance to solve problems which actors cannot solve individually (section 3.1). Next, this alliance should co-create a well-defined shared vision for the future (section 3.2). Then, the alliance should design intervention strategies that have the potential to reach their objective (section 3.3). For the theory of Futures4Food on which this is based, we refer to our final report.

3.1 Build an alliance

Addressing the protein transition could benefit from the involvement of multiple actors who pool their resources in alliances (Bryson et al., 2006; Frame, 2008). This could help to build and strengthen value chains and trust, to facilitate financing, to exchange knowledge, to build projects, and to promote the sector and the protein transition message (Bryson et al., 2006; Technopolis & Blonk Consultants, 2018).

Local examples of learning communities contributing to the protein transition:

- In the tenth Flemish Green Deal named 'Eiwitshift op ons bord' (2021-2025, translated as 'Protein Shift on our plate', henceforth abbreviated as GDPS), 85 organisations signed the agreement to make an effort for accelerating the protein transition (Departement Omgeving, 2021, 2025a).
- 'The Next Food Chain' is a network since 2019 promoting the plant-based sector and is consisting of mostly processors and knowledge institutes (The Next Food Chain, 2019).
- The non-profit organisation 'The Shift' became the national contact point for sustainability (including food topic) and connects over 500 organisations, among others private companies, NGOs, academic institutions and public administrations (The Shift, 2025).
- The 'Belgian Alliance for Climate Action' is a network supporting organisations with setting and achieving science-based emission reduction targets, including food actor members (Belgian Alliance for Climate Action, 2025).

Local examples of multi-partner projects contributing to the protein transition, subsidised by the Flemish government in 2022-2024 (Agentschap Landbouw & Zeevisserij, 2021):

- 'Een boon voor Leuven': about local value chains of plant-based proteins, with Boerenbond vzw, Innovatiesteunpunt vzw, Kortom Leuven cv, ILVO and COOP content cv.
- 'Een boon voor A': mostly about more plant-based dishes in restaurants in Antwerp, with Mosquito in the Room, Metsense, Biopolder, Rurant vzw and Let Us.
- 'PEUL-CHAIN': about stimulating production, processing and consumption of pulses, with Peas & beans, Humus bv, Vlaams Instituut Gezond Leven vzw, ILVO, VLAM, Casibean bv, De paddestoel, Deldiche nv, Solucious nv and Agape.
- 'Een oesterzwam vol eiwitten': about product innovation and consumption acceptance of an oyster mushroom burger, with Brugs Food Lab vzw, Kopje Zwam cvba, Casibean bv, Katholieke Hogeschool Vives and Inagro vzw.
- 'LoCoSoy': about a local value chain of soy, with four farmers (Pollet, Dewaele, Colembi and Beaucarne), La vie est belle, Inagro, ILVO, Biograno, Flanders' FOOD, UCLouvain and Colruyt group.
- 'Nood aan noot': about studying the economic potential of walnuts and hazelnuts cultivation in Flanders, with three farmers (Vets, Erregat en Tennstedt), Praktijkpunt Landbouw Vlaams-Brabant, ILVO, Inagro vzw and Migino bv.
- 'PeaPact': about studying the production of 'gele erwt' (yellow pea) and its consumer acceptance, with farmer Dewaele, HOGENT, Inagro, Bond Beter Leefmilieu, Agrosoft, La vie est belle, De Hobbit, Cosucra and Delifresh.

3.2 Build a shared vision for the future

For becoming transformative, it is also important to work on a well-defined shared vision for the future (Lang et al., 2012).

A local example of building a shared vision:

In the GDPS, this was defined before launching by interacting with actors. Their objective is twofold: (1) to improve the ratio between animal and plant-based proteins in Flemish consumption towards a ratio of 40%/60% animal/plant-based proteins by 2030, and (2) to reduce the total intake of proteins (Departement Omgeving, 2021).

3.3 Build intervention strategies on how to reach that future

After having defined the shared vision, the alliance should design intervention strategies that have to potential to reach their objective (Lang et al., 2012). After performing interventions, actors ideally evaluate the success to redesign new interventions.

3.3.1 Type of interventions

Interventions should ideally be designed to reduce or remove the barriers of consumers depicted in Figure 2. Consequently, the barriers could become enablers that accelerate the protein transition. When designing interventions, it is important to understand the different elements of the food environment. This is the context in which people access and eat food. It includes an external domain (like how available food is, infrastructure, food prices, information and labels, and the social setting) and an individual domain (affordability, accessibility, convenience and desirability) (SAPEA, 2023).

Consequently, when designing interventions, one should take three elements into account according the COM-B model: 'Capability', 'Opportunity' and 'Motivation'. The model assumes that, to trigger behaviour change (Graça et al., 2019):

- Consumers must have the ability to carry out the behaviour, including mental and physical skills;
- The context must support the behaviour by offering opportunities, both social and physical, as part of the external domain of food environment;
- Consumers need to be motivated to carry out the behaviour, involving both conscious decision-making and automatic psychological processes.

Below, we list evidence-based examples of five types of interventions that should ideally be combined into protein transition strategies, resulting in protein-rich diets being easy and preferred by consumers (SAPEA, 2023):

-Price interventions: consumers are more likely to choose plant-based products if animal-based products become more expensive. This can be achieved by food providers or encouraged through government food policies. Setting prices that reflect the true environmental cost of products is economically efficient (Funke et al., 2022). High tax levels on animal products can also help reduce their environmental impact, however, the fairness of these policies should be addressed, for example, by redistributing tax revenue back to citizens (Latka et al., 2021). Reallocating agricultural subsidies could also potentially impact consumer price differences and purchasing behaviour (Broeks et al., 2020).

-Physical availability interventions: increasing the availability of plant-based food and placing it in prominent positions can influence consumers' choices (called 'choice architecture nudges'). An intervention study in a supermarket in 2017-2018 showed an increased sales of plant-based sandwich spreads after adding them in the butchery section next to their equivalent meat products (Coucke et al., 2022). Also offering an attractive ready-made veg(etari)an dish as default could help to change the norm (EIT Food SUCCESS, 2024). These type of interventions can be applied in grocery stores as well as other food settings such as schools and work canteens, and restaurants. Policy could support that by for example making it mandatory for public canteens to offer at least one vegan meal per day.

Further exploration:

Menu card tips for restaurants in Dutch can be found in this link below:

<https://omgeving.vlaanderen.be/sites/default/files/2024-10/>

[Voorbeelden Tien tips voor meer plantaardig op het menu.pdf](#)

-Food composition interventions: developing tasty (and healthy) plant-rich products and meals gives consumers more options to replace meat and dairy. Investments in technology, both public and private, can support these innovations. Quietly reformulating products can help overcome resistance for consumers, but voluntary reformulation by processors has shown limited success. Involving the food industry more broadly, with clear targets and mandatory measures, makes this approach more effective (Leroy et al., 2016).

-Digital food environment interventions: digital tools can be used to increase food availability of plant-based products or meals (Samsioe & Fuentes, 2022), and can provide personalised feedback such as offering food swap suggestions at checkout (Granheim et al., 2022). Also digital content such as online recipes and (personalised) food marketing can be an intervention (Granheim et al., 2022).

-Social environment interventions: the social environment strongly affects consumer choices (Sparkman et al., 2021). Highlighting social norms in interventions is promising in reducing meat consumption (Byerly et al., 2018; Grundy et al., 2022). For example, workplace posters featuring people enjoying vegetables at lunch can be effective (Taufik et al., 2019). Past policies, such as those regulating tobacco, show that social norms can change through combining measures, such as taxes, advertising restrictions, and public smoking bans (Hamilton et al., 2008; Schoenaker et al., 2018).

-Information environment interventions: efforts have largely focused on providing information to consumers, either in the format of labels and scores, advertising regulations, and campaigns. Food health labels have been shown to have a low to moderate effect because they rely on consumers being motivated to use them (Hercberg et al., 2021), and front-of-pack labelling is voluntary in Europe. Still, labelling can have an influence on food reformulation, indirectly improving diets and health (Vandevijvere & Vanderlee, 2019). Warning labels, such as those used in Chile, have shown better results (Reyes et al., 2019). For sustainability labels, evidence is mixed. A clear and consistent approach is needed to avoid confusion with many new sustainability labels emerging (SAPEA, 2023). Using attractive names for foods and dishes is also important: focus on the taste, not on the terms 'vegetarian' or 'vegan' (Mosquito In The Room, 2023).

Campaigns (among others education) can also help clarify the health and ethical aspects of different food categories and can increase cooking skills, but should not be a standalone intervention (SAPEA, 2023).

Local examples of a strategy combining an information environment intervention with a digital food environment intervention:

In the GDPS, it was decided to make a common narrative to advise consumers, since they believed it could contribute to their objective. They have designed the complexity-informed, evidence-based fifty-fifty ('halfhalf') narrative during an intense co-creation process. The 'halfhalf' website is available since 2023 on the web domain of the nonprofit 'Vlaams Instituut Gezond Leven' (Gezond Leven, 2024). Its website launch was combined with a communication campaign in November 2023 towards consumers via social media using videos and e-guides and via physically nudging material in among other supermarkets and canteens (Departement Omgeving, 2024). The different materials are free to use by all actors, inside and outside the GDPS.

Since the fifty-fifty narrative is evidence-based, learnings from the word choices (see Figure 3) are interesting for different actors willing to accelerate the protein transition. The narrative corresponds to the 40/60 ratio and makes it more actionable. It also takes into account many different forms of resistance that people can feel when asked to change their diet. On purpose, it does not contain the terms protein shift or transition (Departement Omgeving, 2023c).

Also in the GDPS, the podcast series 'De eiwitshiffters' was developed in 2024, mostly targeting food professionals (Departement Omgeving, 2025b).

Other examples of communication campaigns in Belgium are 'Week zonder vlees' in October ('Week without meat') (Week Zonder Vlees, 2025) and 'TryVegan' month in November by BeVegan (BeVegan, 2025).

<p>1 Almost all of us like a piece of meat, fish, cheese and a glass of milk.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Target your message to omnivores and flexitarians. Vegetarians and vegans already eat enough plant-based proteins. • Avoid using the words vegetarian, vegan, omnivore, and flexitarian. People don't like to be pigeonholed. • Don't fight positive associations people have with meat, fish, or dairy products.
<p>2 But we all know that too much is never good.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use the gut feeling that most people have: 'of course eating too much meat, fish or dairy is not good' as a starting point for the requested behavioural change.
<p>3 Therefore, half of Belgians no longer eat meat or fish daily. And more and more Belgians say they would like to choose a meal without meat or fish more often.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Make it clear that an important (r)evolution has already taken place in Belgium today. Half of Belgians no longer eat meat or fish every day. • Make it clear that more and more 'people like them' want to take steps in the plant-based direction.
<p>4 That's smart thinking. Because a plant-based meal is not only better for your health. It is also better for your environment and for the climate. But how often should we choose a plant-based meal?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describe a meal without animal protein as a 'plant-based meal'. • Do not use the words flexi, flexitarian or flexitarian. • Avoid the words vegan, veggie, vegetarian and veggie. • Focus on the three main arguments for limiting animal protein intake: health, environmental impact and animal welfare. • Use the words climate and environment when talking about the environment and animal welfare.
<p>5 The new guideline is simple: try to go for fifty-fifty. Choose plant-based meals half of the week.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Don't ask people to give up meat, fish and dairy. • Call on everyone to go for 'fifty-fifty' by turning half of your meals during the week plant-based. • Use the words 'guideline' and 'try'.
<p>6 By the way, choosing plant-based is getting tastier and easier. You can start today by replacing one ingredient, product, or meal. Enjoy!</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emphasise the positive evolution in taste and ease to prepare plant-based meals. • Affirm that every step in the right direction is a good step.

Figure 3: Fifty-fifty, a new narrative for the protein shift in Flanders, in six steps towards effective behavioural change

Source: Departement Omgeving, 2023a

Further exploration:

This flyer is also available in Dutch and French:

https://omgeving.vlaanderen.be/sites/default/files/2023-08/OnePager_Halfhalf_Eiwitshifft.pdf

https://omgeving.vlaanderen.be/sites/default/files/2023-08/OnePager_Moiti%C3%A9moiti%C3%A9_eiwitshifftFR.pdf

3.3.2 Food product categories to promote in interventions

When reflecting on pathways on population level to accelerate the protein transition, one should think strategically about which food product category to promote, since every different protein source could have a different potential to accelerate the protein transition. Still, in a balanced diet, different types of proteins are combined (Hoge Gezondheidsraad, 2019). For this report, we aim for pathways with high potential to accelerate the protein transition in the short term within the Belgian context. Therefore, we do not focus on other possible pathways including **microbial** and **insect** proteins, **cultured** meat and plant-based **fish mimicking** analogues. Yet, we recognise their long term potential (Wullaert et al., 2024). Since the Belgian Superior Health Council (Hoge Gezondheidsraad, 2019) recommends to replace processed and red meat by other protein rich products such as pulses, fish, egg or poultry, we do not focus on **fish** (or other seafood), **egg** or **poultry** reducing pathways specifically. We will not also not focus on dairy reducing pathways, since substituting **dairy** with plant-based products is going at a better pace than substituting meat, and since dairy has a lower protein content (Nubel, 2022). Nevertheless, we acknowledge the environmental, public health and animal welfare repercussions of dairy (Low et al., 2012; Poore & Nemecek, 2018; Springmann, 2024).

To grasp the potential of the possible pathways for promoting different food product categories, we have studied the intention of 18-64 year-old meat-eating citizens of the Flemish Region ('Vlaams Gewest') for consuming different foods through an online questionnaire (2024, n=1050, unpublished). The respondents received different statements and could answer with 'Strongly disagree', 'Disagree', 'Neutral', 'Agree', 'Strongly agree' or 'No idea'. These responses were scaled on the interval [-1;1], with -1 corresponding with 'Strongly disagree' and 1 with 'Strongly agree'. The 'No idea' answers resulted in various lower sample sizes (minimum n=919). Since we were asking about consumption intentions, significant negative average values should be interpreted that on average respondents do not intend to conduct a certain behaviour (being different from a neutral intention, using the one sample t-test).

The first pathway is general **meat reduction** (without per se replacing it). This could be done by eating **smaller portions** of meat and by eating meat **less frequently**. The results of our study show that the average willingness of respondents to reduce meat consumption was significantly positive: 0.09 ($p < .001$). However, effectively planning to reduce meat consumption ('I plan to consume less meat in the near future') did not differ significantly from a neutral stance. Yet, there was a significant positive average willingness to consume smaller portions of meat (0.17) and to consume meat less frequently (0.13).

The second pathway is meat reduction by replacing traditional meat with **hybrid** meat. The latter was defined in the questionnaire as a 'meat product to which also plant-based proteins are added, e.g., a beef hamburger to which pea protein was added'. Hybrid meat products offer a convenient means of reducing meat consumption without sacrificing taste or requiring the development of new cooking skills or habits, while also providing the additional benefits associated with plant-based ingredients (Grasso, 2024). On average, respondents were not willing to replace some meat-based meals by hybrid meat meals in the near future (-0.34). One should be careful with the interpretation of this result, since it might not be clear to the respondents that the taste and texture of hybrid meat is similar to traditional meat.

The third pathway is to replace meat by plant-based food products: either **traditional meat substitutes** (tofu, tempeh, seitan, quorn, soy chunks), **unprocessed meat substitutes** (nuts, seeds, mushrooms, pulses such as peas, lentils, princess beans and white beans), or **meat analogues**. The latter are defined in this report and in the questionnaire as vegetarian and vegan food products that imitate the taste of meat (e.g., vegetarian and vegan burgers, minced meat, sausages and nuggets), but also vegetarian and vegan sandwich fillings (e.g., ham sausage, salami, prepared mince, chicken curry, pate and meat salad). These products could make it easier for meat eaters to consider plant-based products as a substitute for meat as the meal and habit can generally remain the same (Messina et al., 2023). On average, respondents were not willing to replace some meat-based meals with meals containing

plant-based protein sources in the near future: 'traditional meat substitutes (such as tofu, tempeh, seitan, Quorn, soy chunks)' (-0.33), 'unprocessed meat substitutes (such as nuts, seeds, mushrooms, pulses)' (-0.05), and 'meat analogues' (-0.31). In each case, the average value was significantly negative. The willingness to replace meat by traditional meat substitutes and hybrid meat did not differ significantly from the willingness to replace meat by meat analogues (independent sample t-test).

To put these different protein transition pathways into perspective, we also asked the respondents for their intention to **replace meat with high environmental impact (red meat such as beef) by meat with less environmental impact (white meat such as chicken meat)**. It is an interesting pathway for limiting the negative environmental and health impacts, but would result in an increased negative impact for animal welfare and protection, as more individual animals need to be slaughtered per kg of meat (Low et al., 2012; Poore & Nemecek, 2018; Springmann, 2024). There was a significantly positive average willingness to replace high-environmental-impact meat by lower-environmental-impact meat (0.14).

Apart from that, we asked the respondents for their intention to **replace meat by eggs and dairy products such as cheese**. For this pathway, the impact on the environment, health and ethics depend more on the type of product (which type of meat is replaced and which animal-based replacement is chosen) (Low et al., 2012; Poore & Nemecek, 2018; Springmann, 2024). There was a significantly positive average willingness to replace meat by 'eggs and dairy products such as cheese' (0.20). The results clearly indicate that animal-based protein sources are more preferred by the respondents.

If we compare different meat analogues, respondents showed the highest willingness to replace 'processed meat as a snack' by its corresponding meat analogue. However, it seems less beneficial to focus on this category in interventions as the consumption of these meat products was relatively low compared to the other groups (only 12.86% reported consuming meat as a snack at least once a week). Consequently, the impact of replacing them with meat analogues is rather low (Table 2). The second highest willingness to replace meat by its corresponding meat substitute was for 'processed meat in a hot meal'. It might be beneficial for interventions promoting meat substitute consumption to focus on the category of meat analogues for 'processed meat in a hot meal', as this type of meat is consumed a lot. This beneficial intervention was also highlighted in a German study (Michel et al., 2021).

4 Why do Belgian actors want to accelerate the protein transition?

There are several motivations to accelerate the protein transition. To study which motivations are most important to different food actors, we performed face-to-face interviews (24/05/2024-08/07/2024) and an online LimeSurvey questionnaire (19/06/2024-11/08/2024) with 31 different organisations that are participating in the GDPS, both Flemish and Belgian organisations. They included representatives of 8 government bodies (at the level of the Province, Regions and cities), 4 knowledge institutes (a secondary school with food education, higher education and research institutes), 9 non-profit organisations, 3 supermarket chains and 7 other companies (an ingredient supplier, processors, a support company, a caterer and a wholesaler).

Respondents were asked to rate the importance of ten predefined motivations for their organisation to commit to the protein transition, on a scale from 0 (not important) to 10 (very important). There is a wide distribution of the importance of most motivations, except for 'limiting global warming' (Figure 4). The results of the average scores for each motivation were as followed, ranked from higher to lower importance:

- Limiting global warming (highest average score: 8.26)
- Limiting other environmental problems, such as biodiversity loss and soil degradation (7.63)
- Improving public health, such as prevention of lifestyle diseases and antibiotic resistance (7.29)
- Guaranteeing food security for the growing world population (6.47)
- Developing the image of their organisation (6.39)
- Developing the Flemish economy (5.97)
- Improving social justice in the world (5.87)
- Developing economically as organisation (5.27)
- Improving animal welfare and protection (4.97)
- Becoming more strategically independent of other countries (lowest average score: 4.45)

Figure 4: Box plots visualising the distribution of the importance of the ten motivations (y-axis), on a scale from 0 (not important) to 10 (very important) (x-axis)

The box represents the middle 50% of responses, the line inside is the median (middle value), and the whiskers extend to the lowest and highest scores, the dots are outliers.

Source: unpublished work Futures4Food, 2024

To facilitate an overview for comparing the scores across the different actor groups, Figure 5 and 6 were constructed. Some main conclusions:

- As expected, supermarket chains and other companies value the motivation ‘developing economically as organisation’ highly, whereas the motivation ‘becoming more strategically independent of other countries’ is most important to government bodies.
- Interestingly, actor groups supermarket chains and government bodies prioritise motivations ‘limiting global warming’ and ‘limiting other environmental problems, such as biodiversity loss and soil degradation’ the most.
- Intriguingly, the motivation ‘improving public health, such as prevention of lifestyle diseases and antibiotic resistance’ is particularly valued by supermarket chains and non-profit institutes, but is less important to government bodies.

Figure 5: Heatmap visualising the distribution of the importance of the ten motivations (y-axis) across the actor groups (x-axis), on a scale from 0 (not important) to 10 (very important) with darker red indicating higher importance and darker blue indicating lower importance
Source: unpublished work Futures4Food, 2024

Figure 6: Bar chart visualising the distribution of the importance of the ten motivations (y-axis) across the actor groups, on a scale from 0 (not important) to 10 (very important) (x-axis)
Source: unpublished work Futures4Food, 2024

To illustrate the variance across the actor groups for the motivation importance scores, Figure 7 was constructed. The data is most dispersed for the motivation importance for ‘improving social justice in the world’ and ‘guaranteeing food security for the growing world population’ by the supermarket chains. Government bodies have different views on the importance of ‘improving social justice in the world’ as well.

Figure 7: Heatmap visualising the variance of the importance of the ten motivations (y-axis) across the actor groups (x-axis), with darker red indicating higher variance and darker blue indicating lower variance

Source: unpublished work Futures4Food, 2024

5 What issues does the protein transition help to address?

5.1 Limiting global warming

Globally, about one-third of total human-caused greenhouse gas emissions is attributed to agrifood systems. This is equal sized to the emissions of the industrial sectors and the transportation combined (FAO, 2024). 57% to 81% of these food emissions is caused by the production of animal-based food (Leip et al., 2015; Xu et al., 2021), while only supplying for 33% of protein and 17% of calories (FAO, 2022). Consequently, the protein transition can help to limit global warming. If the twofold consumption objective of the GDPS would be reached (see section 3.2), this would result in a greenhouse gas emission reduction of 29% ¹ (Dénos et al., 2024).

The reasons why animal-based products generate significantly higher greenhouse gas emissions than plant-based products can be summarised in three key points. Firstly, ruminant animals (such as cattle, sheep, and goats) produce methane during digestion, and methane is a powerful greenhouse gas. Secondly, the storage, management, and application of manure release methane and nitrous oxide emissions. Thirdly, animals consume large quantities of feed (SAPEA, 2023).

The differences in greenhouse gas emissions between key food products of the protein transition are shown in Figure 8 (Poore & Nemecek, 2018). Despite its processing, in all cases meat and dairy replacement products have a lower greenhouse gas emission than its animal-based counterpart (Springmann, 2024).

¹ This academic paper by Dénoš and colleagues used realistic trade data and assumed that the protein intake was 63 gram per day, which is lower than the current protein intake, but still above the recommended levels set forth by the Superior Health Council.

Figure 8: Greenhouse gas emissions measured in kilograms of carbon dioxide-equivalents across the supply chain per kilogram of food product

Source: Poore & Nemecek, 2018

5.2 Limiting other environmental problems

The protein transition can contribute to limiting environmental problems related to food production, also when including plant-based meat analogues (Clark et al., 2019; Smetana et al., 2021; Tang et al., 2024). In the European Union (EU), the contribution of livestock as compared to the whole agricultural sector is 78% for terrestrial **biodiversity** loss, 80% for **soil** acidification and **air** pollution (ammonia and nitrogen oxides emissions), and 73% for **water pollution** (both nitrogen and phosphorus) (Leip et al., 2015). Globally, about 50% of the habitable land is used for agriculture and 77% of this agricultural **land** is used for livestock (FAO, 2022). For obtaining this livestock land, substantial deforestation happened (FAO, 2006). Furthermore, compared to plant protein production, intensive animal protein production requests 10-1000 times more **water** (Aiking, 2011).

5.3 Improving public health

The results from the BNFCs 2022-2023 as described in section 1.3 are not conform with the dietary recommendations of the Belgian Superior Health Council (Hoge Gezondheidsraad, 2019). Reducing meat consumption and total protein consumption is encouraged for health benefits, also if this is meat is replaced by plant-based meat analogues (Bryant, 2022). Particularly, the consumption of red meat is discouraged, as it increases the risk of mortality, coronary heart disease, colorectal cancer, type II diabetes and stroke (Clark et al., 2019).

While shifting to more plant-rich diets, consumers and actors can be concerned about the **protein quality**. This is determined by two factors. Firstly, the protein **digestibility**. There is little evidence for a difference between plant-based and animal-based products regarding digestibility (Mariotti & Gardner, 2019).

Secondly, the protein quality is determined by the presence of essential **amino acids** (type and amount). Amino acids are the building blocks of proteins. The composition, sequence and structure differ across foods. Out of the 20 amino acids that are found in the human body, five amino acids are sufficiently produced by the human body itself (non-essential), six amino acids cannot be sufficiently produced in certain physiological or pathological conditions (semi-essential) and the other nine amino acids cannot be produced by the human body itself (essential), see Table 4. Regarding amino acid distribution profiles, it is less optimal for plant-based foods compared to animal-based foods, so containing less favourable proportions (EFSA NDA Panel, 2015).

Table 4: Amino acids present in human proteins

<u>Non-essential amino acids</u>	<u>Semi-essential amino acids</u>	<u>Essential amino acids</u>
Alanine	Arginine	Histidine
Aspartic acid	Cysteine	Isoleucine
Asparagine	Glutamine	Leucine
Glutamic acid	Glycine	Lysine
Serine	Proline	Methionine
	Tyrosine	Phenylalanine
		Threonine
		Tryptophan
		Valine

Source: EFSA NDA Panel, 2015

One method used by the FAO and the World Health Organisation (WHO) to calculate the protein quality is the Protein Digestibility-Corrected Amino Acid Score (PDCAAS) in which the most limiting essential amino acid is taken into account (FAO Expert Consultation, 2013). In general, the PDCAAS of animal-based products is higher than that of plant-based products, except for products based on soy (Hoge Gezondheidsraad, 2016). Chicken egg protein has a score of 100%, beef 92%, soy 91%, wheat 42% and pulses range from 31% to 58% (Hoge Gezondheidsraad, 2016). The PDCAAS method has its shortcomings, among which the bioavailability of amino acids that is not adequately taken into account and the overestimation of protein quality of products containing antinutritional factors (FAO Expert Consultation, 2013). The Digestible Indispensable Amino Acid Score (DIAAS) tackles some shortcomings of PDCAAS and is therefore a more recent protein quality measure used by the FAO (FAO Expert Consultation, 2013). Using DIAAS instead of PDCAAS results in lower values for plant protein (Hoge Gezondheidsraad, 2016). Nevertheless, not one specific method has been found to be ideal. Despite most plant-based products having a specific limiting amino acid, an extensive and varied plant-based diet provides a complete amino acid intake. All essential amino acids can be sufficiently consumed and deficiencies in protein intake can be thus avoided by combining plant-based products (Mariotti & Gardner, 2019; Pyett et al., 2023). According to Mariotti & Gardner, protein quality should be seen as part of an overall diet quality instead of on its own (Mariotti & Gardner, 2019).

Despite the high protein consumption in Belgium, actors can be concerned about the **protein concentration** in plant-based food. There are big differences in **these concentrations**, both when comparing animal-based with plant-based foods, and when comparing within these categories. In general, animal-based products have a higher protein content than plant-based products, however cow's milk has a low protein concentration. Protein rich foods include fish, pulses, meat, eggs, and nuts and seeds. Crops with a high protein concentration (>20% in dry composition) are soy, peas, canola, chickpeas, fava beans, lentils, lupins, mung beans, white beans, peanuts, sunflower and almonds. Crops with a medium concentration (10-20%) are wheat, corn, oats and quinoa. Of all the crops mentioned, soy, peas, canola, white beans, sunflower, oats and quinoa have the most favourable PDCAAS (≥ 0.6) (Good Food Institute, 2021; Nubel, 2022).

Further exploration: For more details on the nutrition aspect of food, we refer to Nubel vzw.

On population level, reducing intensive animal production for food would be beneficial for the antimicrobial resistance and zoonotic diseases (The World Bank, 2010; Van Boeckel et al., 2015).

5.4 Guaranteeing food security for the growing world population & improving social justice in the world

The protein transition in high-income countries could increase food security —“a situation in which all people at all times have access to adequate quantities of safe and nutritious food to lead a healthy and active life” (FAO, 2025a, p1)— because animal agriculture is high resource intensive compared to plant-based agriculture (as stated in the previous sections), and because the protein transition could limit the expected increase in food prices (Aiking & de Boer, 2020).

As the pollution from the animal industry and its working conditions are disproportionately impacting marginalised communities, especially in the Global South, the protein transition could improve social justice (Chamanara et al., 2021; Johnston & Cushing, 2020; Ramos et al., 2021). Of course this should be nuanced and carefully considered in the transition, since livestock can contribute to store wealth and function as insurance, especially in low- and middle-income countries (Baltenweck et al., 2020; Herrero et al., 2013).

5.5 Developing the economy: developing the image of organisations, developing economically as organisation, developing the Belgian economy, becoming more strategically independent of other countries

Organisations could enhance their image by contributing to accelerating the transition towards more plant-based consumption. It could show their commitment towards the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs, see section 6.1.1). Moreover, in a competitive market a compelling brand purpose can differentiate an organisation (van Langen, 2024).

In addition, producers of primary food commodities —like vegetables, fruits, grains, pulses, seeds, nuts and aquatic plants— could benefit from a growing demand by the protein transition. Also food processing companies and ingredient providers could develop economically by contributing to for example plant-rich meat or fish replacements, plant-based dairy and egg replacements and plant-rich spreads and nut and seed pastas. If profit margins of plant-rich foods are advantageous, also other chain actors (like wholesalers and retailers) could benefit (Wullaert et al., 2024). Consequently, as a result of the protein transition, the economy in Belgium could gain from this and could becoming more strategically independent of other countries (Agentschap Landbouw en Zeevisserij, 2025), among others by reducing reliance on imported animal feed (e.g., soy from South-America).

5.6 Improving animal welfare and protection

Since the 1960s, animal farming in developed countries has become increasingly industrialised. In the drive for greater efficiency, livestock production has intensified, with animals being bred to grow faster and kept in more confined spaces to maximise output and lower costs (Thornton, 2010). At the same time, substantial evidence indicates that birds, mammals, and fish utilised and killed for food are sentient and capable of experiencing consciousness (Low et al., 2012) As a result, most ethical perspectives suggest that industrial animal farming is morally indefensible (Bekoff, 2009; Francione, 1995). The protein transition supports ethical practices by reducing dependence on factory farming (Aiking & de Boer, 2020), therefore protecting their health and welfare (FAO, 1994).

6 (Inter)governmental policy initiatives

Plans of action to facilitate a more sustainable food system are increasingly being developed on multiple scales by different governments. However, not all policies are in accordance with each other. Aligning all relevant policies would increase the success rate of the protein transition. For example, EU policies affecting the production and consumption of plant-based proteins have not been coordinated. Innovative policy instruments that radically change the current animal-focused food system are currently not applied (SAPEA, 2023). As a final example, subsidies on both European and Flemish level are awarded to projects and campaigns promoting meat and dairy production and consumption (European Commission, 2022), and at the same time some money is invested in European and Flemish Green Deals (see section 6.2.2 and 6.4.3) (Departement Omgeving, 2021; European Commission, 2025i).

In order to create an overview of the currently existing policy initiatives that influence the protein transition in Belgium, policy initiatives are first discussed on the international level, followed by the EU level, the Belgian level, the regional level (Flanders, Wallonia, Brussels-Capital) and finally the local level (cities).

6.1 International

The United Nations (UN), an international organisation that currently comprises of 193 Member States including Belgium, gathers around worldwide problems to work on shared solutions. The UN consists of a number of Funds, Programs and Specialised Agencies which help achieve the UN goals (United Nations, 2025b). One of those relevant for the protein transition is the UN Environment Programme that facilitates the sustainable development of the global environment (UNEP, 2025).

UN Member States are bound in the UN Charter, an instrument of international law concerning international relations. Sustainable development and climate action are jointly on their agenda, as the two are interconnected and both vital to the well-being of humanity now and in the future. Another global issue on their agenda is food, as since the mid-2000s food prices began to fluctuate heavily and world food markets changed dramatically, undermining food security and nutrition (United Nations, 2025a).

The ‘State of Food Security and Nutrition in the World 2020 report’ underlines the importance of diet quality, sustainability and transformation of entire food systems with specific solutions differing from country to country. This report encourages governments to support sustainable, local and small-scale producers to grow and sell more nutritious foods and secure their access to markets (FAO, IFAD, UNICEF, WFP and WHO, 2020)

6.1.1 Sustainable Development Goals

In 2015, the UN decided on 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) targeting the global challenges we face that form the new global sustainable development agenda for 2030 (UN Department of Economic and Social Affairs, 2015). The SDGs are widely used as a pillar for the development of sustainability projects. The protein transition can contribute to at least these SDGs: ‘Zero hunger’ (SDG2), ‘Good health and well-being’ (SDG3), ‘Decent work and economic growth’ (SDG8), ‘Industry, innovation and infrastructure’ (SDG9), ‘Responsible consumption and production’ (SDG12), ‘Climate action’ (SDG13), ‘Life below water’ (SDG14), ‘Life on land’ (SDG15) and ‘Partnerships for the goals’ (SDG17) (Aiking & de Boer, 2020; European Commission, 2025d).

The UNEP Brussels Office works closely with EU institutions to combine forces and work on shared goals. Together they support the implementation of the SDGs and the alignment with relevant initiatives such as the European Green Deal (see section 6.2.2) (UNEP, 2025).

Further exploration:

All SDGs and their subgoals can be found in Dutch, French and English on the Belgian website <http://www.sdgs.be>.

6.1.2 Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change reports

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change is created by the UNEP and the World Meteorological Organisation. Their reports serve as reference works for policy makers, researchers and other specialists. In the sixth and latest assessment report (2022) about the mitigation of climate change, the role of sustainable healthy diets and the transition to more sustainable food sources is emphasised (Shukla et al., 2022).

6.1.3 World Health Organisation research

The World Health Organisation (WHO) is a UN Specialised Agency with the mission to attain the highest level of health for everyone everywhere, by connecting countries, people and partners (WHO, 2025). The WHO has a science division that validates public health guidance and turns innovations into real-world solutions, and another division that delivers reports on data trends and analysis related to global health. For example, the WHO researches the negative health effects of meat (e.g., carcinogenicity) (WHO, 2015) and other negative effects of the production and consumption of meat, such as environmental sustainability, inequality, (animal) welfare and noncommunicable diseases and gives advice on meat alternatives (WHO, 2025).

6.2 European Union

The European Union (EU) is an economic and political union of 27 European countries including Belgium (European Union, 2025a). The Member States have given the EU the authority to pursue common policy in a number of areas. For agriculture, the EU has 'shared competences'. This means that the EU can only act in the areas the EU Member States have authorised the EU to do so, through the EU treaties. In these treaties, it is specified who can pass laws in what areas: the national governments, the EU or both (European Commission, 2025a).

An example of food labelling: the Court of Justice of the European Union (Case C-438/23 | Protéines France and Others, p1) stated that "where no legal name has been adopted, a Member State may not prohibit the use of terms traditionally associated with products of animal origin to designate a product containing vegetable proteins". In this example, it was advantageous for the plant-based meat and dairy sector that the EU could decide over this topic and not individual countries, as some of the countries were not in favour of meat-like names on plant-based products (CURIA, 2024).

Below, we discuss EU policy elements that are relevant to the protein transition.

6.2.1 EU Common Agriculture Policy

The EU defined and implemented the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), EU's oldest and costliest policy. The objectives of the CAP are, among others, to increase agricultural productivity, to ensure a fair standard of living for farmers, to stabilise markets, to secure food supply and to assure reasonable prices (European Union, 2025b).

The CAP has evolved along with the EU, mentioning sustainable production and strict standards concerning the environment and animal welfare (European Commission, 2025j). The reformed CAP (2023-2027) aims to be fairer, greener and more performance-based, securing the future of agriculture and forestry and achieving the objectives of the European Green Deal and its strategies (including the Farm-to-Fork strategy, see section 6.2.2) (European Union, 2025b).

One objective of the CAP Strategic Plans is to increase competitiveness and improve the position of farmers in the food chain, both in the short and long term. The Coupled Income Support (CIS) is a tool to achieve this. Member states can choose the financial allocation for the CIS per agricultural sector. On average the Member States allocate 70% of the CIS budget to livestock, 14% to protein crops, 3% to cereals, 3% to rice and 5% to fruit and vegetables. Flanders allocated its whole CIS budget to livestock, while Wallonia decided to allocate 3% to protein crops and legumes (e.g., soy, lentils, chickpeas) and the remaining 97% to livestock (European Commission, 2022).

6.2.2 European Green Deal and Climate Law

The European Green Deal has been first set up in 2019 to transform the EU into a modern, inclusive, resource-efficient and an economically competitive continent with net zero emissions of greenhouse gases by 2050. The European Commission proposed to take actions in eight fields, among which climate and agriculture. All European sectors have to reduce their emissions, including the agricultural sector. The Green Deal furthermore focuses on sustainable food systems and healthy and affordable food. The EU wants to accelerate and navigate necessary transitions and engage citizens in social innovation (European Commission, 2025i).

To write the goals set out in the European Green Deal into law, the European Climate Law came into force in 2021. Apart from the climate neutrality target by 2050, the law also establishes an interim target of reducing net greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% by 2030, compared to 1990 levels (European Commission, 2025c).

Part of the European Green Deal is the Farm-to-Fork Strategy, which focuses on resilient food systems (European Commission, 2025d). The aim is to make the food system more fair, healthy and environmentally friendly and accelerate the transition to a sustainable food system. The Farm-to-Fork strategy describes four important aspects of sustainable food systems: (1) sustainable food production, (2) sustainable food processing and distribution, (3) sustainable food consumption and (4) food loss and waste prevention. The Farm-to-Fork strategy sets actions and targets, and both regulatory and non-regulatory initiatives are set up. Explicit mentions to the protein transition are limited, but occur in the following chapters: (European Commission, 2025i)

- The 'sustainable food production' chapter mentions the transition towards more sustainable feed, the promotion of sustainable livestock production and sustainable aquaculture (e.g., algae);
- The 'stimulating sustainable food processing, wholesale, retail, hospitality and food service practices' chapter mentions more sustainable marketing standards (e.g., discourage strategies such as cheap meat) and reinforcing the role of sustainability criteria;
- The 'promoting sustainable food consumption and facilitating the shift to healthy, sustainable diets' chapter mentions transitioning to a more plant-based diet, with less red and processed meat.

Implicit references can be found as well, e.g., in animal welfare, pesticide and fertiliser usage, labelling, pricing and taxes (European Commission, 2025i). Most of these ideas are not (yet) translated into legislation (European Commission, 2025d).

The CAP aims to align with the European Green Deal, however, several shortcomings raise doubts about the compatibility of the objectives of these two policies, as the CAP is not adapted to reduce agricultural emissions (Payne, 2024).

As a consequence of among others the COVID-19-pandemic, the Russia's war on Ukraine and the protests of the farmers, criticism has emerged about the 'Farm-to-Fork' strategy harming food security. As a result, the European Commission launched a Strategic Dialogue in January 2024 about the future of EU agriculture with various actors to explore methods of ensuring a fair standard of living for farmers, while adhering to climate targets (EPRS, 2024). It is stated in the concluding report of this Dialogue that "the European Commission should develop, by 2026, an EU Action Plan for Plant-based Foods to strengthen the plant-based agri-food chains from farmers all the way to consumers" (Strohschneider, 2024, p55). It is recommended to make the healthy and sustainable choice the easy one, helping consumers to embrace the transition towards more plant-based protein intake. The report also notes: "As this transition will impact the income and economic viability of livestock farmers and producers, it is important to use the Agri-food Just Transition Fund to support those affected" (Strohschneider, 2024, p54).

In 2025, organisations urge the new European Commissioner for Agriculture and Food to follow the recommendations from the Strategic Dialogue and consequently keeping the agenda for this EU Action Plan for Plant-based Foods (BEUC, 2025). Nevertheless, in February 2025, the European Commission publishes the Vision for Agriculture and Food without explicitly mentioning the protein transition. Moreover, it is stated that "the Commission will work on strengthening the competitiveness and resilience of sensitive sectors such as livestock" (Ch 3.2.b), (...) "Livestock is and will remain an essential part of EU agriculture, competitiveness and cohesion" (Ch 3.2.b). Still, the Vision mentions the SDGs, animal welfare and "prevailing emissions from livestock" (Ch 3.3). Apart from that, it encompasses "building trust and dialogue across the entire agri-food system, in the EU and globally" (Ch 1) (European Commission, 2025b).

6.2.3 EU Circular Economy Action Plan

In the Circular Economy Action Plan (2020), food is considered as one of the key product value chains for more circular products. However, the focus is on packaging and food waste reduction, while protein production and consumption patterns are not targeted at this EU level. The role of agriculture in air pollution is acknowledged, and measures to mitigate emissions of livestock are offered (e.g., closed storage of manure, improved livestock feeding strategies). Nevertheless, a reduction of the size of livestock is not conveyed (European Commission, 2020a).

6.2.4 EU Regulation On Deforestation-Free Products

The EU wants to halt the consumption of products that drive deforestation. The EU 'Regulation on Deforestation-free Products' apply to, amongst others, cattle and soy (European Commission, 2025h), consequently indirectly influencing the protein transition. As of the 30th of December 2024, it is prohibited to market these goods and derived products if they are not (1) deforestation-free, (2) not produced in line with the local legislation of producing countries or (3) not covered by a due diligence statement indicating no more than a negligible risk of non-compliance. Apart from aiming for reducing deforestation, it is also expected to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and biodiversity loss (Regulation (EU) 2023/1115, 2023).

6.2.5 EU Industrial Emission Directive

With the 'Industrial Emission Directive' launched in 2010, the EU wanted to limit harmful emissions (air pollutants, wastewater discharges and (toxic) waste) from industries, with a focus on energy production and material efficiency and reuse. In 2024, it was revised into the 'Industrial and Livestock Rearing Emissions Directive'. A total of 37,000 industrial installations and 38,500 pig & poultry farms are currently required to operate under a specific permit (European Commission, 2024d).

6.2.6 EU Taxonomy Regulation for sustainable activities

In line with the European Green Deal objectives, the 'EU Taxonomy Regulation' is a tool since 2020 to help investments in economic activities that drive the transition towards more sustainability. This taxonomy classification system defines criteria for activities in line with a net zero trajectory by 2050, and other environmental goals. It defines terms such as 'sustainable agriculture'. This regulation helps scaling up sustainable investments, by securing investors against greenwashing, by mitigating market fragmentation and by creating clear criteria for companies to become more climate-friendly (European Commission, 2024b).

6.2.7 EU Novel Food regulation

The European Commission is responsible for approval and cataloguing of novel foods. The latter are "foods that had not been consumed to a significant degree by humans in the EU before 15 May 1997" (European Commission, 2025g, p1). Novel foods cannot be sold unless the application is approved by the European Commission and the European Food Safety Agency (FOD Volksgezondheid, Veiligheid van de voedselketen en Leefmilieu, 2021). Most plant-based innovations were not classified as novel foods and could consequently be marketed quickly. Some plant-based and alternative protein sources (like cultured meat, edible insects, fungi and algae) are deemed novel foods, consequently slowing down its time-to-market, while ensuring food safety (Lähteenmäki-Uutela et al., 2021).

6.2.8 EU Directive on CSRD and CS3D

The Directive on Corporate Sustainability Reporting (CSRD) of the European Commission will also have an indirect influence on the protein transition, as more and more companies will among others need to report the impact of their activities on the environment (European Commission, 2023).

Between 2027 and 2029, also large EU and non-EU companies will have to apply the EU Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive (CSDDD or CS3D). This Directive (2024/1760) has the aim to stimulate sustainability in companies' operations and across their global value chains (European Commission, 2024a).

6.2.9 EU Dietary guidelines

The area of public health is the sole responsibility of national governments. The EU can complement national policies, but only to reach shared objectives and to tackle commutual problems. The same goes for nutrition policy, as the EU considers Food-Based Dietary Guidelines (FBDGs) to primarily inform citizens of a specific country or region, with specific food availabilities, diet-health relationships, diet-related health problems and food culture. All EU countries have FBDGs, yet, not all countries discuss the limitation of meat and benefits of a plant-based. If present, the guidelines for pulses and animal-based products are more or less in the same trend for the different countries: consume more pulses and less (fat, red or processed) meat. In Belgium, it is recommended to consume "up to 300g of

red meat per week (beef, pork, veal, mutton, and goat meat and horse meat)” and “limit the consumption of processed meat to 30g per week (smoked, dried or salted for preservation purposes or treated with (chemical) preservatives such as nitrites or nitrates)” (European Commission, 2024c, p1).

6.2.10 EU subsidies for research and training

‘Horizon2020’ was the EU’s research and innovation funding program from 2014 until 2020. A number of relevant projects for the protein transition were set up under this program (European Commission, 2020b). A relevant example is ‘FOOD2030’ (since 2016), aiming to enhance policy coherence and transform food systems. It links multiple sectors of the food system, from production to consumption. The FOOD2030 program had four priorities: sustainable, affordable and healthy diets; climate friendly and sustainable, ecological food systems; circular food systems and; innovation and reinforcing of communities. These priorities beg the sourcing and development of new protein alternatives to foster plant-based diets and dietary shift (European Commission, 2025e). To implement the ‘FOOD2030 policy framework’, ‘FIT4FOOD2030’ is working on sustainable food system networks and engaging actors (FIT4FOOD2030, 2025).

‘Horizon2020’ was succeeded by ‘Horizon Europe’ (2021-2027), the new research and innovation program to foster new partnerships and projects in and between industries and countries (European Commission, 2021). European partnerships in food, bioeconomy, natural resources, agriculture and environment are set up under Horizon Europe, however, thus far the production of animal-based products is mostly safeguarded (European Commission, 2025f).

A relevant research committee is the ‘Standing Committee on Agricultural Research’, an EU source of advice on European agricultural and more generally on bioeconomy research since 1974. This committee also supports the coordination and integration of national research programs. Its focus is on sustainable food systems, with collaborative working groups on sustainable animal production and animal health and welfare research (SCAR, 2025).

6.3 Belgian federal government

The federal government is responsible for the compliance of policies with the decisions of the EU and the UN. Still, federal competences are limited when it comes to the protein transition, as most related competences are divided in the Regions (Belgian Federal Government, 2025; De Bauw et al., 2025).

Further exploration:

More information on the competencies and policies related to sustainable healthy food environments in Belgium can be found in this 2025 report:

www.sciensano.be/en/biblio/

[fragmentation-transformation-multi-level-policy-mixes-sustainable-healthy-food-environments-belgium.](#)

6.3.1 Federal sustainable development policy

A relevant federal policy is the sustainable development policy that covers the aspects of environment, climate, biodiversity conservation and animal welfare. Sustainable production and processing of foods are mostly targeted (Geenens et al., 2025).

In 2007, the commitment of Belgium was reinforced by the explicit inclusion of sustainable development in the Belgian Constitution. It was from then on recognised as a general policy objective. Consequently,

commitments are expected of the federal state and the three Regions (Flanders, Wallonia and Brussels-Capital Region), who each have their own sustainable development policy (Geenens et al., 2025).

In 2017, Belgium published its first 'National Voluntary Review' (NVR), showing the implementation of the EU Agenda 2030 in the Belgian sustainable development policy and in the functioning of the federal governmental services. The NVR is a follow-up and review mechanism for countries that are engaging in the Agenda 2030 and also facilitates sharing experiences, pitfalls and successes between countries to accelerate sustainable development (United Nations High Level Political Forum, 2017). The Belgian NVR also explains how it elaborates the SDGs in Belgian context in order to serve as a frame to put the SDGs in practice. Under SDG2 'End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture' it is explained that Belgium focuses on innovative value chains, integrated solutions and systematic innovations in the food chain. The link between diet, health and ecosystem sustainability is stressed. Alternative forms of protein such as algae, plants and insects are mentioned as a solution together with higher efficiency throughout the different links in the food chain. SDG 9 'Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialisation and foster innovation' mentions the BRAIN-be framework program for research for projects aligning research potential with social needs in areas of competence on the federal level. SDG 13 'Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impact' does mention measures that have been taken for the agricultural sector, but does not further specify the measures. The other relevant SDGs (3, 8, 12, 14, 15 and 17) do not mention specific actions or frames for the protein transition in Belgium (United Nations High Level Political Forum, 2017).

In November 2020, in the general policy note of the 'Belgische Kamer van Volksvertegenwoordigers' ('Chambre des représentants') concerning climate, environment, sustainable development and the Green Deal in Belgium, some of the SDGs and its subgoals were criticised for not being sufficiently concrete. The relance plan and transition priorities for sustainable development, elaborated together with the regions and local governments, were suggested tools to help reach these goals (Belgische Kamer van Volksvertegenwoordigers, 2020). The respective policy note of 2022 states that Belgian policy initiatives became more concrete (Belgische Kamer van Volksvertegenwoordigers, 2022).

In the Coalition Agreement ('Regeerakkoord') in 2020 and 2025, the federal government stated its ambition to reduce the Belgian greenhouse gas emissions with 55% by 2030 and to be climate neutral by 2050. It also declared to fully stand behind the EU Green Deal (and thus the Farm-to-Fork strategy) and the Paris Agreement. A concrete strategy is lacking (Belgian Federal Government, 2025; Federale Regering, 2020).

6.3.2 Federal climate policy

The EU recommends their Member States to shape a National Energy and Climate Plan with the aim to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. In 2021, Belgium complied. The plan contains contributions from the Federal state, the Flemish, Walloon, and the Brussels-Capital Region. In the latest actualisation (2023) of the Plan, food is mentioned a few times, but no concrete targets are stated (Federale Overheid, 2025).

Belgium does not have a climate law on federal level (European Parliament, 2024) and is not on track for climate neutrality by 2050 (Bureau fédéral du Plan, 2024). Since 2021, the Belgian Climate Centre is established, as part of the federal implementation plan. Their mission is to enhance the influence of scientific research on climate mitigation and adaptation in Belgium, thereby facilitating an effective and socially equitable transition (Belgian Climate Centre, 2025).

6.3.3 Federal dietary guidelines

The topic of nutrition is allocated to the Federal Public Service (FPS) of Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment. This FPS mentions striving for reduction of greenhouse gas emissions, but do not mention the protein transition specifically (FPS Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment, 2025).

The Belgian Superior Health Council developed the food-based dietary recommendations for Belgian adults in 2019. The focus is on consuming more plant-based products: at least 125 gram of whole grain products, 250 gram of fruit, at least 300 gram of vegetables and 15 to 25 gram of nuts or seeds each day, and pulses at least once a week. Processed and red meat should be limited and replaced by other protein rich products such as pulses, fish, egg or poultry (Hoge Gezondheidsraad, 2019).

The visual representation of these recommendations is named 'Épi Alimentaire' or 'Voedingstak'. Other visuals have been developed by the Regions, helping to identify healthy diets: 'Pyramide Alimentaire' in French and 'Voedingsdriehoek' in Dutch (FAO, 2025b). Since 2021, the Flemish 'Voedingsdriehoek' ('Food triangle') is also explicit about the ecological reasoning behind eating more plant-based (Gezond Leven, 2025a). Consequently, it is a valuable communication tool supporting the protein transition. The Walloon 'Pyramide Alimentaire' does not explicitly mention the ecological reasoning, but it complies with the recommendations of the Belgian Superior Health Council (Apaq-W, 2025).

6.3.4 Federal subsidies for research and training

Two scientific bodies are linked to the FPS Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment and conduct research into policy-supporting matters: Sciensano and the Superior Health Council (FPS Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment, 2025). Sciensano, the Federal Research Centre, among others carries out the National Food Consumption Survey ('Voedselconsumptiepeiling', 'Enquête de Consommation Alimentaire') every 10 years, including the plant-based versus animal-based consumption (Sciensano, 2025). The Superior Health Council ('Hoge Gezondheidsraad', 'le Conseil Supérieur de la Santé') draws up scientific advisory reports to guide policy makers towards certain priorities in the decision making process (Superior Health Council, 2025).

BELSPO, the Belgian Science Policy Office of the federal government, is among others also funding the research project SUSFOODBEL on the topic 'Transitioning to healthy diets from sustainable food systems in Belgium: priority policy actions and their multiple sustainability impacts' (BELSPO, 2023). In 2026, the project will result in concrete policy recommendations. No specific federal subsidies were found to provide plant-based training for chefs.

6.4 Flemish government

The Regions in Belgium (Flemish Region, Walloon Region and Brussels-Capital Region) are competent for among others agriculture, economy, the environment, their provinces and municipalities (Vlaamse Overheid, 2025a).

6.4.1 Flemish sustainable development policy

The Regions also translate the SDGs into their own objectives and implement them in their policy. In 2018, the fourth and latest Flemish Strategy for Sustainable Development encompasses both 'Vision 2050' ('Visie 2050') and 'Focus 2030' ('Vizier 2030'). Yet, the Strategy does not prioritise the protein transition (Vlaamse Regering, 2018a, 2018b).

6.4.2 Flemish food strategy

The Flemish government has put the food system on the agenda in the coalition agreement of 2019-2024. The aim was to develop a strong, integrated food policy which contributes to making the food system in Flanders more sustainable (Vlaamse Regering, 2019). In November 2022, the Flemish Food Strategy 'Go4Food' was launched (Department of Agriculture & Fisheries, 2023). The preparations for Go4Food consisted of two elements. Firstly, a call for ideas from Flemish citizens and companies to contribute to the Flemish Food Strategy ('voedselveranderaars', 'food changemakers') was launched. Secondly, there was the kick-off of a 'Food Coalition' ('voedselcoalitie') to work on the Food Strategy policy. This Food Coalition is transdisciplinary, with among others members from the Flemish government, knowledge institutes and other actors in the food sector. One of the Go4Food strategy working paths is about sensitising healthy and sustainable diets (Department of Agriculture & Fisheries, 2023).

Part of the Go4Food strategy is the 'Flemish protein strategy', with among others an extensive group of partners from the agri-food chain, knowledge institutes and the Flemish government. The strategy consists of six strategic themes: sustainable feed, sustainable livestock production, more plant-based proteins, more novel proteins, more product diversification and sustainable consumption (*Agentschap Landbouw en Zeevisserij, 2025*).

Further exploration:

All actions under the banner of the Flemish protein strategy are documented in an interactive dashboard, showing that there are 122 actions (including some overarching GDPS actions) and 95 research projects related to proteins since the launch of the Protein Strategy in 2021 (data retrieved at 28/05/2025) (Agentschap Landbouw en Zeevisserij, 2025).

6.4.3 Flemish Green Deal Protein Shift on our plate

The Flemish Department of Environment initiated the Flemish Green Deal 'Protein Shift on our plates' (GDPS, 2021-2025, see section 3), contributing to the sustainable consumption theme of the Flemish protein strategy. Multiple meetings, workshops, and events each year result in new collaborations, exchanges, and the development of a common narrative (see section 3.3.1). The GDPS yearly reports provide an overview of all activities and actions (Departement Omgeving, 2021, 2022, 2023b, 2024).

The GDPS steering committee includes representatives from eight different organisations: three government agencies, two higher education institutes and three nonprofits. A steering member with a key role is the Flemish Institute for Healthy Living ('Vlaams Instituut Gezond Leven vzw') (Departement Omgeving, 2021). This institute is not an official body of the Flemish government, but a recognised umbrella organisation that supports the Flemish policy on health promotion and illness prevention (Vlaamse Overheid, 2025b). The institute has among others organised a communication campaign about promoting the consumption of pulses in 2023, 2024 and 2025 ('Week van de Peulvrucht') (Gezond Leven, 2023, 2025b; Vlaamse Overheid, 2024).

6.4.4 Flemish climate policy

The Flemish Energy and Climate Agency provides policy support and implements the energy and climate policy in Flanders (Vlaams Energie- en Klimaatagentschap, 2025). Flanders does not have its own climate law (European Parliament, 2024).

6.4.5 Flanders circular economy

Circular economy is one of the Flemish transition priorities to reach the Flemish sustainability goals. The transition partnership 'Vlaanderen Circulair' is working on this theme since 2017 thanks to the Department of Economy, Science and Innovation. The food chain is one of its six central themes. Regarding the protein transition, they work on diversifying the protein offer and make the consumption of proteins more sustainable (Vlaanderen Circulair, 2025).

6.4.6 Flemish subsidies for research and training

The Flemish government signed in on the EU 'FIT4FOOD2030' project to organise a regional policy lab to implement the FOOD2030 policy. This multi-actor platform mainly served to get a better view on the multitude of regional strategies and policy plans, and to align them in order to create maximum impact with research and investments (Vlaamse Overheid, 2021).

The Flemish government is subsidising ILVO, being a knowledge institute for agriculture, fishery and food research. They are conducting research on among others the health aspects of food, resilient food systems and protein diversification for food and feed (ILVO, 2025).

In addition, VLAM is committed to promoting Flemish food products and its image both nationally and internationally through Flemish subsidies (VLAM, 2025). NICE, the Flemish information centre for food, is part of VLAM and actively communicates and informs about more sustainable, local and diverse protein sources and how to implement these into your diet. Still, their communication is more on animal-based products compared to plant-based (NICE, 2025; VLAM, 2024).

Flanders is also providing subsidies for organisations such as Good Planet, ProVeg and BeVegan to among others provide training for schools and chefs (Departement Cultuur, Jeugd & Media, 2021; Good Planet, 2025; ProVeg, 2025).

6.5 Walloon government

6.5.1 Walloon sustainable development policy

The Walloon administration ('Service Public Wallonie', SPW) is an important actor contributing to the implementation of the sustainable development agenda by emitting and implementing public policies. In 2012, a dedicated department was established within the SPW to ensure a greater dynamic and consideration of the SDGs: 'Direction du Développement durable'. It has specific arrays of action, including a sustainable food system (Wallonie service public, 2025a).

The 3rd Walloon sustainable development strategy was adopted in September 2022. It compiles the different strategic plans that exist in Wallonia and organises them according to the different SDGs (Wallonie service public, 2022b).

6.5.2 Walloon food strategy

In April 2018, 'Le Référentiel – Vers un système alimentaire durable en Wallonie' was launched and divided into several strategic and operational objectives, two of which concerns the protein transition: 'Strengthening the fodder and protein autonomy of livestock farming in Wallonia' & 'Increase consumption of fruits and vegetables as well as water'. It laid the foundations for the Walloon government's vision in terms of sustainable food (Service Public de Wallonie, 2018).

In May 2018, a Walloon development strategy of vegetal proteins was developed: 'Développement des protéines végétales en Wallonie'. This plan aims at the development of production and adapted value chains with the specific target of increasing annual protein crop planting with 15000 ha by 2030 (Collège des producteurs, 2018).

In 2020, a Sustainable Food Council has been established ('Collège wallon de l'Alimentation Durable'). It ensures that the challenges that food system actors must face are taken into account and it stimulates the partnership dynamic between actors for accelerating the transition (Service Public de Wallonie, 2025).

In October 2022, the sustainable food action plan is adopted, called 'Food Wallonia'. It sets up the framework for a collaboration of three ministries towards sustainable food. It doesn't specify the inclusion of plant proteins, but mentions a path towards sustainable and healthy diets. The ambitions of Food Wallonia all contribute to the 'Référentiel - Vers un système alimentaire durable en Wallonie' (Wallonie service public, 2022a).

6.5.3 Walloon Green Deal Sustainable Canteens

'Green Deal Cantines Durables', the first Walloon Green Deal (2019-2024), was a partnership that brings together four types of actors: canteens, central kitchens and catering companies, supply and logistics players, and political authorities. They contribute to six areas of work: local and seasonal products, products that respect the environment and animals, fair trade products, healthy, balanced and tasty meals, the reduction of food waste, as well as social inclusion. The Sustainable Canteen Label can be obtained by canteens after meeting strict criteria (Manger Demain, 2025).

6.5.4 Walloon climate policy

In contrast to Flanders and the federal level, Wallonia does have a climate law that aims for climate neutrality by 2050: 'Décret Neutralité Carbone' since 2023, indirectly influencing the protein transition (European Parliament, 2024; Wallex, 2023). Also in 2023, Wallonia adopted the 'Plan Air Climat Energie' (SPW Energie, 2023).

6.5.5 Walloon circular economy

In 2021, the Walloon Region adopted a Circular Economy strategy ('Circular Wallonia – Stratégie de déploiement de l'économie circulaire'), with the agri-food sector being one of the priority sectors. It is coordinated by Wagralim, the Excellence technological pole in Wallonia, equivalent to Flanders' FOOD (Wagralim, 2025).

6.5.6 Walloon subsidies for research and training

On the initiative of the Minister of Sustainable Development, calls for food relocation projects have been launched ('Soutenir la relocalisation de l'alimentation en Wallonie') (Wallonie service public, 2025c). In the 2020 call, 46 projects were financed, including piloting for the production of plant proteins in Wallonia in partnership with CePiCOP ('Centre Pilote Céréales et Oléo-Protéagineux') and FEGRA (FWA, 2024). In the 2023 call, the financial support was channelled to infrastructure projects and to four prioritised sectors: cereals, vegetable protein, fruits and vegetables (Wallonie service public, 2025c).

A relevant research example is 'PROTEWIN', a 'Strategic Innovation Initiative' ('Initiatives d'Innovation Stratégiques') since 2023 to contribute to the protein independence of the Walloon Region through the

deployment of the vegetable and alternative protein sector while offering new technological solutions for manufacturers in the sector in order to accelerate the emergence of the sector and the creation of added value. It is supported by all Walloon research networks (Wallonie service public, 2025b).

Apart from that, 'WALOPEA' (2022-2024) was a project that wishes to ameliorate the value chain of human consumption protein crops. It gathered three actors: Wagralim, Cra-W ('Centre wallon de Recherches agronomiques') and CePiCOP (Wagralim, 2022). No specific Walloon subsidies were found to provide plant-based training for chefs or to directly promote the consumption of plant-based food.

6.6 Brussels-Capital Region government

6.6.1 Brussels-Capital sustainable development policy

In 2020, 'Go4Brussels 2030' was introduced as a strategy to promote sustainable and harmonious development in the region, supporting Brussels in its shift towards a sustainable economy. The protein transition is not mentioned explicitly (Brussels Capital Region, 2020).

6.6.2 Brussels-Capital food strategy

The 'Good Food 2 strategy' is the food strategy of the Brussels-Capital Region since 2022 and plans to run until 2030. It was collaboratively co-constructed representing the entire food supply chain and governmental bodies (Good Food Brussels, 2025c).

The strategy defines a 'Good Food' plate as healthy and tasty, with a strong emphasis on whole grains, nuts, pulses, vegetables and fruits. It is prepared with fresh, seasonal, preferably organic and as many local ingredients as possible. It limits salt, sugars, fatty foods, animal proteins (less and of better quality), as well as food waste (Good Food Brussels, 2025c).

The strategy is operationalised through four cross-cutting principles and five strategic axes. Goals in the axes of the strategy that concern the protein transition are: (Good Food Brussels, 2025c)

- Axis 2: developing 'Good Food channels' to supply Brussels, among others
 - o Operationalising B2B service that helps to connect the offer to the demand.
- Axis 3: ensuring the distribution of a 'Good Food' offer, among others
 - o Increasing the number of public and school canteens that offer a vegetarian choice every day.
 - o Providing training to canteens and restaurants.
 - o Providing labels for canteens and restaurants with specific sustainability criteria with a scale of 1 to 3 indicating how well they are doing. To obtain the 'Good Food Resto label' the menu should be at least 15% vegetarian every day. To obtain the 'Good Food Cantine label' there should be at least one vegetarian meal per week if the canteen provides 1 or 2 meal options per day, and at least one vegetarian meal per day if it provides 3 or more meal options per day (Good Food Brussels, 2025b, 2025a).
- Axis 4: ensuring 'Good Food' for everyone, among others
 - o Increasing the accessibility of 'Good Food' in neighbourhoods.
 - o Providing education and support in schools (including lunch boxes, snacks, vegetable gardens).
 - o 50% of the people living in Brussels applying a flexitarian diet (min. 3 days/week without meat or fish).
 - o 30% of the people living in Brussels consuming less dairy.
 - o Financing non-profit organisation ProVeg through an annual subsidy to support the 'JeudiVeggie' campaign.

6.6.3 Brussels-Capital climate policy

Just like Wallonia, Brussels-Capital Region has a climate law that aims for climate neutrality by 2050: 'Le Code Bruxellois de l'Air, du Climat et de la maîtrise de l'Energie (CoBrACE)', indirectly influencing the protein transition (Bruxelles Environnement, 2024; European Parliament, 2024). It was already launched in 2013. 10 years later, Brussels adopted the 'Plan régional Air-Climat-Énergie' (SPW Energie, 2023).

6.6.4 Brussels-Capital circular economy

From 2016 to 2020, the government of the Brussels-Capital Region adopted the Brussels Regional Program for a Circular Economy, including food measures (Be Circular, 2025).

6.6.5 Brussels-Capital funding for research and training

The Brussels-Capital Region government (Innoviris) is funding the 'BrusselsFood2050' project (2023-2026) concerning prospective reflections on the road to a sustainable supply of the region by 2050, including aspects of the protein transition (SYTRA, 2024). Next to that, 'Bruxelles environnement' ('Leefmilieu Brussel') is providing project subsidies to ProVeg vzw, supporting the protein transition (ProVeg, 2025).

6.7 Local governments

Local governments can also play an important role in the protein transition. Up to 65% of the SDG targets are at risk if local urban actors are not given a clear mandate and role in the implementation process (adelphi & Urban Catalyst, 2015).

6.7.1 Flemish local governments

The Flemish Region works closely together with the local governments for a holistic implementation of the SDGs and other established goals. The VVSG, the Association of Flemish Cities and Municipalities, helps to build networks of and for local authorities to work on common goals, such as local food strategies. This association is an important, strategic neutral player that makes the connection between different actors in the local food system (VVSG, 2024).

Individual cities can also contribute to the protein transition in multiple ways. The city of Leuven, Bruges, Ghent, Hasselt, Antwerp and Ostend became partners of the GDPS and stated their own commitments. Cities are for example supporting schools and restaurants, adapting their own catering and participating in the VeggieChallenge in March (Departement Omgeving, 2025a).

6.7.2 Walloon local governments

In 2019, the Walloon region has adopted a sustainable food policy strategy 'Eat Tomorrow' ('Manger Demain'). This strategy coordinates among others the Food Policy Counsels ('Conseil de Politique Alimentaire wallon'). These Counsels represent a new place of local food governance. They are collaborative governance structures that bring together actors from the same territory and revolve around the different dimensions of food, including the preservation of the environment (Géoportail de la Wallonie, 2025). There are among others Food Policy Counsels in Liège Métropole and in Namur (Liège Métropole, 2025; Ville de Namur, 2025).

6.7.3 Brussels-Capital local governments

The City of Brussels developed a 'Climate Plan' with 'Food and urban agriculture' as one of the themes, including 'more vegetarian food'. Their protein transition related targets for 2030 are '3 vegetarian meals a week in schools' and '150 horeca shops and establishments awarded the Good Food label' (City of Brussels, 2025).

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8 Appendices

Appendix 1: List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full form	First mentioned
BNFCS	Belgian National Food Consumption Survey	Section 1.3
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organisation	Section 1.4
UN	United Nations	Section 1.4
MRPS	Plant-rich meat replacement products	Section 2.1
GDPS	Tenth Flemish Green Deal named 'Eiwitshift op ons bord', 2021-2025, translated as 'Protein Shift on our plate'	Section 3.1
EU	European Union	Section 5.2
WHO	World Health Organisation	Section 5.3
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals	Section 5.5
UNEP	UN Environment Programme	Section 6.1
CAP	Common Agricultural Policy	Section 6.2.1
CIS	Coupled Income Support	Section 6.2.1
FBDGs	Food-Based Dietary Guidelines	Section 6.2.9
NVR	National Voluntary Review	Section 6.3.1
FPS	Federal Public Service	Section 6.3.3
SPW	Service Public Wallonie	Section 6.5.1
CePiCOP	Centre Pilote Céréales et Oléo-Protéagineux'	Section 6.5.6

Appendix 2: List of actors

We do not intend to provide a complete list of actors engaging in accelerating the protein transition in Belgium, as it for example does not include restaurants and farmers, but to provide an elaborate overview.

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